

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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预测俄罗斯经济中外国直接投资的动态
**FORECASTING THE DYNAMICS OF FOREIGN DIRECT
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摘要。外国直接投资是许多国家经济增长和发展的重要因素，俄罗斯也不例外。然而，自 2014 年以来，俄罗斯一直面临制裁压力，这对其经济增长产生了负面影响，包括外国直接投资的涌入。本文旨在分析制裁限制对俄罗斯经济外国直接投资流入的影响，并评估其现状和未来接收潜力。

研究结果表明，对俄罗斯实施制裁对该国经济增长和外国直接投资流入产生了负面影响。制裁的后果是造成商业环境的不确定性，增加在俄罗斯经商的成本，并降低来自不友好国家的投资者的信心。近年来，流入俄罗斯的外国直接投资大幅减少。然而，由于俄罗斯拥有丰富的自然资源、熟练的劳动力和战略位置，因此具有巨大的外国直接投资潜力。此外，俄罗斯政府已采取措施改善该国的投资环境，吸引友好国家的外国直接投资。此外，俄罗斯经济目前正在进行重大改革，包括制定与友好国家关系的新规则和彻底现代化基础设施。

关键词：外国直接投资、俄罗斯经济、投资环境、经济制裁。

Abstract. *Foreign direct investment is an important factor in economic growth and development for many countries, and Russia is no exception. However, since 2014, Russia has been under sanctions pressure, which has negatively affected its economic growth, including the influx of foreign direct investment. The purpose of this work is to analyze the impact of sanctions restrictions on the influx of foreign direct investment into the Russian economy with an assessment of the current state and the potential for their receipt in the future.*

As a result of the research, it was established that the introduction of sanctions against Russia had a negative impact on the country's economic growth and the influx of foreign direct investment into its economy. The consequences of the introduction of sanctions were the creation of uncertainty in the business environment, an increase in the cost of doing business in Russia and a decrease

in the confidence of investors from unfriendly countries. In recent years, the influx of foreign direct investment into Russia has decreased significantly. However, Russia has significant potential for foreign direct investment due to its rich natural resources, skilled workforce and strategic location. In addition, the Russian government has taken steps to improve the investment climate in the country and attract foreign direct investment from friendly countries. In addition, the Russian economy is currently undergoing significant reforms, including the creation of new rules for relations with friendly countries and a radical modernization of infrastructure.

Keywords: *foreign direct investment, Russian economy, investment climate, economic sanctions.*

Introduction

Foreign direct investment (FDI) is a critical component of modern international economic relations. Through FDI, foreign investors gain a stake in the host country's companies or assets and thus become active participants in the host country's economy. FDI brings not only financial resources, but also technology, managerial know-how and access to global markets, which can help improve the competitiveness of the host country's economy.

FDI played a significant role in the development of the Russian economic system. Russia has attracted significant amounts of FDI over the past few decades. This has led to the growth of the banking, finance and insurance sectors. FDI has also contributed to the modernization of financial and industrial-technological infrastructure in Russia. The country has made significant progress in attracting FDI by creating a favorable investment climate and increasing economic and political stability. However, today the level of FDI in the Russian economy remains relatively low compared to developed countries.

The Russian economy has faced a number of challenges in recent years, including economic sanctions, the COVID-19 pandemic and fluctuating hydrocarbon prices. According to the World Bank, Russia received \$20.6 billion in FDI in 2020. This was down from a year earlier due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and global economic uncertainty. In recent years, Russia has been subject to unprecedented economic sanctions from the United States and the European Union, which are affecting the flow of FDI into the country. Despite these challenges, the Russian economy remains an attractive destination for FDI due to its large consumer market, significant natural resource reserves and favorable strategic location. The Russian government has taken steps to mitigate the impact of sanctions (introducing tax incentives and initiatives to improve the investment climate, carrying out regulatory reform) and attracting FDI from friendly countries. Overall, FDI remains an important factor in economic growth and development.

In the modern Russian economy there are opportunities for FDI, especially in the field of financial technology, the development of high-tech and knowledge-intensive industries, digitalization and sustainable finance.

It is worth noting that FDI in the Russian economy has been unstable over the past decade and has been heavily influenced by external factors such as economic sanctions and fluctuations in commodity prices. Sanctions restrictions imposed against Russia by the US and EU in response to a special military operation have had a significant negative impact on FDI inflows. Many Western investors have withdrawn or reduced their investments in Russia. At the same time, many investors from friendly countries are gradually increasing their participation in this process.

Obviously, the ability to attract FDI into the Russian economy will depend on a number of factors, including geopolitical events, the country's economic performance and the government's commitment to reform.

Literature review

In recent years, a number of interesting studies have emerged regarding the theory and practice of FDI. In particular, the degree of impact of FDI on domestic investment in the economy was studied [1]. It is due to the presence of technological advantages of foreign investor companies over national companies. This can be considered a factor in crowding out national investment by foreign investors. Increasing technological gaps between countries may lead to structural distortions in global FDI. In this case, some countries will become stable net exporters of them, while others will become net net importers. Also, it is proposed to link the issues of optimizing FDI flows with the problems of achieving macroeconomic balance in the global and national economy [2].

Of significant interest are studies related to the analysis of the role of developing countries in the FDI system. So, I.V. Andronova points out that Chinese investors have serious support from the state. This ensured the competitiveness of Chinese TNCs in the global market, and the country's investment policy could lead to the displacement of European investors from the global FDI market [3].

In modern geopolitical conditions, FDI flows may change under the influence of sanctions imposed on the recipient country of investments, since, as noted by S.V. Kazantsev, the investor is forced to evaluate the various consequences of his own resistance to sanctions, as well as possible losses and benefits [4]. As the number of countries subject to economic sanctions increases, the geographic structure of FDI may change significantly. Against the background of these changes, later in the literature various aspects of investment activity in integration associations were also considered. Such activities are a preferential model and contribute to the development of the economies of the countries of the integration group [5, 6]. In general, the relevance of the problems discussed above is increasing, since with the introduction of sanctions restrictions, the approaches and models of organizing

and planning FDI on the part of TNCs are changing. This is undoubtedly reflected in the sectoral and country structure of FDI.

An important modern challenge for FDI flows is the active development of global digital platforms. Cross-border online sales platforms make it much easier for companies to enter foreign markets. In this case, there is no need to open production in these markets [7]. Therefore, the classic model of organizing foreign production based on FDI of transnational corporations is being replaced by new models. The latter are based either on a smaller volume of physical assets or are based entirely on intangible assets. This allows companies to quickly bypass traditional barriers to entering new foreign markets.

An essential aspect of FDI analysis is the impact on their dynamics and the nature of scientific and technological progress. In foreign literature [8, 9, 10] it is noted that since the 70s of the last century in the USA and EU countries there has been a tendency to increase investment in intangible assets, which now exceed capital investment in material production. At the same time, there is some evidence of the impact of increased investment in intangible assets on the transmission of monetary policy, in particular, its impact on investment and asset prices in the United States for 1990-2017 has been empirically and comprehensively studied. It has been found that for companies with more intangible assets, their investments and stock prices are less dependent on monetary policy [11]. In turn, companies with more intangible assets attract relatively less borrowed funds, since intangible assets themselves are not good collateral for debts [12, 13]. The work [14] substantiates the decrease in the response of FDI to significant changes in monetary policy by the ongoing scientific and technical progress and the growth of intangible assets in the capital structure of companies. Therefore, intangible investments need to be stimulated by instruments of fiscal policy rather than monetary policy, for example, tax incentives for R&D, as well as structural reforms aimed at supporting innovation. This approach is especially relevant for EU countries, which traditionally lag behind the United States both in terms of innovative development in general and in the context of investments in the intangible sphere.

The considered approaches contributed to the formation of a holistic view of FDI, however, in the context of geopolitical instability and overcoming the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, it seems necessary to supplement and clarify certain provisions related to new strategies for attracting FDI.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is economic forecasting of FDI inflows to Russia. To achieve it, two interrelated tasks will be solved. On the one hand, a scientifically based assessment of the influx of FDI is given, based on the modern features of this process, and on the other hand, promising areas of investment activity are selected taking into account forecast estimates. Along with this, an important task of forecasting FDI inflows is to identify factors that have a significant impact on their

attraction. Studying the dependence of FDI on the influence of significant factors is an effective method of obtaining information about the motives for investing capital by foreign investors.

Materials and methods

The sanctions had a negative impact on the country's economy and financial system, making it less attractive to foreign investors. Despite this, some key industries, such as energy, oil production, pharmaceuticals, mechanical engineering and a number of others continue to attract significant volumes of FDI. The influx of FDI into the financial system has continued due to the various strengths and advantages that the country possesses. It is likely that ongoing efforts will be required to address the factors that influence potential investors' choice preferences and encourage increased investment.

An analysis of the threats and challenges faced by FDI in the Russian economy has revealed a number of key factors that may affect the attractiveness of the Russian market for foreign investors. These include economic uncertainty and a complex regulatory environment, which has become more pronounced in the context of sanctions imposed against Russia. A lack of transparency in the business environment and an ambiguous legal framework can pose significant risks for foreign investors. The emergence of new financial technologies and increased competition from other emerging markets may also threaten Russia's ability to attract FDI. To reduce these risks and attract more FDI, Russia needs to address these issues and create a more favorable investment climate, ensure transparency and certainty in the regulatory environment, and strengthen legal protection.

Assessing the possibilities of attracting FDI into the Russian economy is fraught with significant difficulties and uncertainties. While the Russian government has taken steps to improve the country's investment climate and attract foreign investment, ongoing sanctions and geopolitical tensions have had a negative impact on investor confidence and the business environment. In addition, the Russian economy is in the process of modernization, which poses significant regulatory and structural challenges that may pose barriers to attracting FDI. However, long-term prospects will depend on a number of factors, including the evolution of the geopolitical situation, the success of ongoing economic reforms and the ability of the Russian government to provide a stable and predictable investment environment. Overall, the trajectory of FDI in the Russian economy will depend on a complex set of political, economic and regulatory factors, and investors will need to carefully assess both the risks and opportunities before making investment decisions in this area.

Results and discussion

To create a model for forecasting the volume of foreign direct investment inflows into the Russian Federation, we will use the classical approach to estimating linear regression parameters based on the least squares method (LSM). The

construction of this regression model for the purpose of further forecasting will be carried out using the application software package for econometric modeling GRETL (GNU Regression, Econometrics and Time-series Library).

To identify the dependence of the influx of foreign direct investment, the author selected the following factors: GDP growth rate (%), GDP per capita growth rate (%), Growth rate of average monthly nominal accrued wages of employees of organizations in the economy as a whole (%), Inflation growth rate, GDP deflator (%), Expenditures on research and development (% of GDP), Population unemployment rate (%), Gross domestic savings (% of GDP), Labor force (thousand people), Accumulated investments in fixed capital with participation foreign investors (billion rubles), Accumulated investments in fixed assets with the participation of Russian investors (billion rubles), Growth rate of organizations' turnover (%), Growth rate of cash income and expenses of the population (%).

Using data from the Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation and statistics from the World Bank and the Central Bank of the Russian Federation for 2010-2023. We compiled Table 1.

The first stage of the analysis is the selection of factors that most significantly influence the size of FDI, for their subsequent inclusion in the regression model equation. This step was carried out based on the P-value of the coefficients of the variables. After repeated attempts to build a meaningful model, the author proposed the use of eight variables (see Table 2).

Table 1
Initial data for forecasting

Year	FDI inflow, billion rubles	GDP growth rate (%)	GDP per capita growth rate (%)	Wage growth rate (%)	Inflation growth rate, GDP deflator (%)	Research and development expenditure (% of GDP)	Population unemployment rate (%)
2010	46308,5	4,50	4,5	5,2	14,2	1,13	7,47
2011	55967,2	4,26	4,2	2,8	15,9	0,6	6,52
2012	68103,4	3,52	3,8	8,4	8,9	1,3	5,46
2013	72985,7	1,28	1,5	4,8	5,3	1,8	5,48
2014	79030,0	0,73	-1,1	1,2	7,5	1,1	5,16
2015	83087,4	-2,83	-2,3	-9,0	7,2	1,1	5,65
2016	85616,1	0,2	-0,1	0,8	2,8	0,4	5,62
2017	91843,2	1,8	1,6	2,9	5,3	1,5	5,26
2018	103861,7	2,8	2,7	8,5	10,0	0,9	4,84
2019	109608,3	2,2	2,1	4,8	3,3	1,04	4,59
2020	107658,1	-2,7	-2,5	3,8	0,9	1,1	5,72
2021	135773,8	5,9	6,2	4,5	19,1	1,0	4,81
2022	155188,9	-1,2	-0,9	0,3	15,7	1,0	3,96
2023	172148,3	3,6	3,9	7,7	7,0	1,1	3,18

Table continuation 1

Year	Gross Domestic Savings (% of GDP)	Number of labor force (thousand people)	Investments in fixed assets with the participation of foreign capital (billion rubles)	Internal capital investments (billion rubles)	Organizational turnover growth rate (%)	Growth rate of monetary income and expenses of the population (%)
2010	22,6	75478	125	9152	121,11	113,3
2011	24,4	76952	134	11035	107,55	109,7
2012	24,5	76881	195	12586	111,96	105,9
2013	23,1	76553	197	13450	114,70	104,5
2014	22,2	76325	160	13902	104,93	102,8
2015	21,8	76588	117	13897	107,98	110,0
2016	22,9	76034	93	14748	108,21	109,6
2017	24,0	75871	87	16027	110,37	107,3
2018	20,8	75519	44	17782	111,28	104,4
2019	22,7	75398	84	19329	112,94	104,0
2020	23,5	74923	52	20393	114,68	109,9
2021	23,2	75350	65	23239	115,92	104,4
2022	22,3	74924	75	27865	117,68	109,4
2023	23,7	74327	287	31271	118,40	110,7

Source: compiled by the author based on data from the Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation (<https://rosstat.gov.ru/statistics/accounts>) and the Central Bank of the Russian Federation (<http://www.cbr.ru/statistics/?Pr-Id=svs>).

Dependent variable - FDI inflow (billion US dollars), independent - GDP growth rate (%), GDP per capita growth rate (%), growth rate of average monthly nominal accrued wages of employees of organizations in the economy as a whole (%), rate inflation growth, or GDP deflator (%), unemployment rate (%), accumulated investments in fixed capital with the participation of foreign investors (billions of US dollars) and accumulated investments in fixed assets with the participation of Russian investors (billions of US dollars) . Let us accept the probability of erroneous rejection (rejection) of the hypothesis at a 5% significance level.

Table 2
Analysis of regression model variables using LSM

Variables	Coefficient	Art. error	t-statistic	P-value
const	-41,1752	14,4856	-2,780	0,0214
GDP growth rate (X1)	-37,6174	4,03276	-9,080	7,94e-06
per capita GDP growth rate (X2)	39,0191	4,08051	9,926	3,81e-06
accumulated investments in fixed capital with the participation of Russian investors (X3)	0,004808	0,000823055	5,566	0,0003

accumulated investments in fixed capital with the participation of foreign investors (X4)	-0,038351	0,0104080	-3,765	0,0045
growth rate of average monthly salary salaries of employees of organizations in the economy as a whole (X5)	0,295713	0,121193	2,523	0,0326
inflation rate (X6)	0,198128	0,0824025	2,303	0,0467
unemployment rate (X7)	-4,917060	1,71455	-3,016	0,0146

To build a more accurate forecast, all eight variables were tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF test) and KPSS. Based on their results, the stationarity of the observed time series of all variables was proven and it was determined that these series do not contain a trend. The test proved the significance of all variables.

The next stage of analyzing the influence of factors on FDI is assessing the quality of the resulting model (see Table 3).

Table 3
Results of regression analysis of the model using LSM

Secondary manager variables	0,218647	Statistical deviation of dependent variables	18,93419
Amount sq. leftovers	239,1129	Statistical error of the model	5,154425
R-square	0,958314	Corrected R-square	0,925892
F(7, 9)	29,55718	P-value (F)	0,000016

The percentage of error that is allowed in the regression model is determined by the P-value parameter; it should be less than 0.05, which means that the model error level should not exceed 5%. In the constructed model, P-value = 0.000016, which allows us to conclude that the model as a whole is significant. Also, if you pay attention to the coefficient of determination (R²), you can also conclude that the model is good, since the value reaches 95.8%. The coefficient of determination shows the proportion of variation in the resulting trait under the influence of the factors being studied. Thus, about 96% of the variation in the dependent variable is taken into account in the constructed model and is due to the influence of seven selected factors. The Standard error parameter contains sample standard deviations for each coefficient of the regression equation and standard errors of the coefficients. If the standard error is greater than the absolute value of the regression coefficient, the coefficient is insignificant. In the above model, the standard error is 5.154, which is lower than the regression coefficient (R-square = 0.958), therefore, according to this criterion, the constructed model is reliable.

The next step is to check the feasibility of the prerequisites for constructing a regression model using LSM for the absence of multicollinearity and autocorrelation of the residuals, for the normality of the distribution of residuals and for the presence of homoscedasticity, as well as checking the specification of the model. As a result of the analysis, the following test results were obtained (see Table 4).

Table 4
Checking the feasibility of the prerequisites for building a regression model using LSM in the GRETL program

Multicollinearity	
GDP growth annual	191,716
GDP percapita growth annual	222,623
Zarplata rost	4,671
d_Inflation GDP deflator annual	1,383
Un employment total of total l	7,932
d_Investicii v osn kapital	2,027
Vnytrennie kapitalov l	7,162
Breusch-Pagan test for heteroskedasticity Null hypothesis: no heteroscedasticity	
p-value	0,942374
White's test for heteroscedasticity Null hypothesis: no heteroscedasticity	
p-value	0,691207
Ramsey test (RESET) Null hypothesis: specification is adequate	
p-value	0,941306
Durbin-Watson statistics Null hypothesis: there is no autocorrelation of residuals	
p-value	0,948517
Lewing-Box Q-statistic Null hypothesis: there is no autocorrelation of residuals	
p-value	0,057
Test for normal error distribution Null hypothesis: errors are normally distributed	
p-value	0,548437

When building a forecast based on a regression model with multicollinear factors, it is necessary to evaluate the situation based on the magnitude of the forecast error. If its value is satisfactory, then the model can be used despite multicollinearity.

A key prerequisite for constructing a model using the LSM method is also the condition of homoscedasticity. The Breusch-Pagan and White tests proved

the presence of homoscedasticity, since the calculated P-value (0.942 and 0.691, respectively) in each test performed turned out to be greater than the probability of error, that is, the null hypothesis of the absence of heteroscedasticity was accepted.

Let's carry out the Ramsey test (RESET), which is used in econometrics to test the functional form (specification) of the model. Since the P-value (0.941) is greater than the probability of error, the null hypothesis about the adequacy of the specification is accepted, which indicates that the functional form of the given model is acceptable. The test proved the correct choice of the type of connections and relationships between the elements of the model, as well as the correct choice of essential variables and parameters.

An important prerequisite for constructing a qualitative model using LSM is the independence of the values of random deviations from the values of deviations in all other observations, that is, the absence of autocorrelation of residuals. The absence of autocorrelation of residual values ensures the consistency and efficiency of estimates of regression coefficients. Let's check the presence of autocorrelation of the residuals using the Durbin-Watson and Lewing-Box tests. The calculated P-value in both tests (0.949 and 0.057, respectively) is greater than the error rate, thus there is no autocorrelation of the residuals in the model.

When analyzing the quality of the model, it is necessary to test a number of statistical hypotheses using the Fisher and Student tests, which can be used in the case when the residuals are distributed according to the normal law. Analysis of the normality of the distribution of residuals showed a value (p-value = 0.548437) that is greater than the probability of error, that is, the residuals are distributed normally.

Thus, as a result of testing the feasibility of the LSM assumptions when assessing the reliability of the regression model, the author proved their feasibility and the correctness of the model. The regression coefficients found based on the system of normal equations are unbiased, effective and consistent, which allows us to proceed to the regression equation and the interpretation of its coefficients for the variables:

$$y = -41,175 - 37,617 \times X_1 + 39,019 \times X_2 + 0,0048 \times X_3 - 0,0383 \times X_4 + 0,2957 \times X_5 + 0,1981 \times X_6 - 4,9171 \times X_7 \quad (1)$$

The coefficients of the regression equation can be interpreted as follows: with an increase in the growth rate of GDP per capita by 1%, the amount of FDI increases by 39.019 million rubles, and with an increase in the growth rate of the country's GDP by 1%, it decreases by 37.617 million rubles. With an increase in accumulated investments of "Russian" origin in fixed capital by 1 million rubles, the influx of FDI into Russia increases by 4.8 thousand rubles. Increase in accumulated foreign investment in fixed assets by 1 million rubles. causes a drop in FDI inflows by 38.3 thousand rubles. With an increase in the growth rate of average

monthly nominal wages by 1%, FDI inflows increase by 295.7 thousand rubles, and with an increase in the growth rate of inflation by 1% - by 198.1 thousand rubles. An increase in the unemployment rate in Russia by 1% causes a decrease in FDI inflows into the country by 4.9171 million rubles. Consequently, the analysis carried out using LSM revealed the main dependencies and patterns of formation of the amount of FDI inflow into the Russia.

Conclusion

Based on correlation and regression analysis of the forecast model in relation to data for the Russian Federation, a high degree of dependence between GDP and FDI in the country for 2010-2020 was identified, and a forecast model of FDI inflows into the Russian economy was built for the period from 2021 to 2023. The dependent variable was FDI inflow (billion rubles), and the independent variables were the GDP growth rate (%), the growth rate of GDP per capita (%), the growth rate of the average monthly nominal accrued wages of employees of organizations in the economy as a whole (%), GDP deflator (%), unemployment rate (%), accumulated investments in fixed capital with the participation of foreign investors (billion rubles) and accumulated investments in fixed capital with the participation of Russian investors (billion rubles).

In the constructed model, about 96% of the variation in the dependent variable is taken into account and is due to the influence of seven selected factors, which indicates the good quality of the constructed model. As a result of checking the feasibility of the LSM assumptions when assessing the reliability of the regression model, the author proved their feasibility and the correctness of the model. The regression coefficients found based on the system of normal equations are unbiased, effective and consistent. Thus, the analysis of the influx of foreign direct investment into Russia using the LSM revealed the main dependencies and patterns of formation of the magnitude of their inflow.

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